

Transforming Feature Models to Decision Models – Algorithms and Examples

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I. INTRODUCTION

Based on the findings from Czarnecki et al. [1], we argue that anything that a feature model captures as variable features can in principle be captured in a decision model. However, actually transforming a feature model into a decision model is far from trivial as also the specifics of the respective modeling approaches have to be taken into account. We describe our algorithms to generate a decision model from a feature model in detail and use a running example to explain the transformations made by the algorithms.

We will transform the Wiki engines feature model by Acher et al. [2] into a decision model, which conforms to the DOPLER decision model approach [3]. Even though the term “feature” is highly overloaded among different modeling approaches [4], in the Wiki engines (cf. Figure 1) example, a feature is clearly a technical property of a software system. In contrast, a decision model focuses on the decisions that are needed to derive products, by answering a set of predefined questions [1], [5]. The Wiki engines feature model is shown in Figure 1 and an example of a decision model conforming to the DOPLER approach [3] by Grünbacher et al. [6], [7] is shown in Table I.

Features can be optional (e.g., Unicode) or mandatory (e.g., RSS). All feature modeling approaches support a tree-like hierarchical organization of features as an essential concept. Child features can be grouped under a parent feature. Groups can be defined as Or (1 to n of the features in the group can be selected; e.g., LicenseCostFee or Storage or both can be selected) or Xor (1 to 1, meaning exactly one of the features in the group can be selected; e.g., exactly one License must be selected and exactly one Language can be selected), or with a certain cardinality (n to m, meaning between n and m child features of the group can be selected; e.g., none or exactly one LicenseCostFee feature must be selected). Different feature modeling approaches provide different constraint languages to restrict the legal configurations of features [1]. In our example, several implies (I), excludes (E) and bidirectional implies (BI) constraints have been defined. For example, the Unicode feature implies the Language feature and vice versa (BI) and the DifferentLicenses feature excludes the GPL feature and vice versa (excludes constraints are bidirectional by default).

In DOPLER [3], a decision is specified by a unique id

and its decision type. This defines the range of values which can be assigned to a decision. DOPLER provides Boolean, String, Number, and Enumeration decisions (cf. Table I). A decision can be represented using arbitrary text, usually a question. Decisions usually depend on each other. For instance, a decision can be a prerequisite for other decisions or a decision can constrain other decisions. For this purpose, DOPLER provides visibility conditions and rules. A visibility condition defines for a decision when it becomes relevant and can be answered during product derivation, thus defines a hierarchy and order for making decisions. For example, a decision about the authentication support for the *Configuration Wizard (CW)* only makes sense to be made, if the CW has been selected before (cf. Table I). A DOPLER rule is executed after a decision is made, for example, if a decision is about whether all tools shall be included in a derived product and this decision is set to true, all separate decisions to include certain tools are automatically set to true too (cf. decision *ALL* in Table I).

An essential difference between feature modeling and decision modeling is that *common features*, e.g., RSS in Figure 1, are outside the scope of decision modeling. Also, while in feature modeling, *hierarchy* is essential and has uniform semantics (child-presence-to-parent-presence implications), it is secondary and has varied semantics (child-to-parent-presence or child-to-parent-visibility implications) in decision modeling. Further differences depend on the range of supported *data types*, the way in which *constraints* (among features or decisions) can be described. In our example, the feature model has implies and excludes constraints. A DOPLER decision model allows to define visibility conditions and rules in a domain-specific language close to Java (described by Dhungana et al. [3] in detail). A visibility condition evaluated to true means the decision is shown to users during product derivation, whereas a condition evaluated to false means the decision is not shown to users (i.e., the feature is mandatory and no decision needs to be made). A decision with visibility false can be compared to a state variable.

The transformation algorithms presented below are specified for the DOPLER decision model approach and its constraint language [3]. However, we think many transformation concepts can be generalized to other approaches, which is part of our future work.

Bi Implies: Storage <--> Unicode; Community <--> FileRCS; Commercial <--> US; FileRCS <--> Perl; Unicode <--> Language; US <--> Java

Implies: GPL2 --> PHP; GPL --> Storage

Excludes: DifferentLicenses --> GPL; Database --> Python; NoLimit --> DifferentLicenses; Unicode --> NoLimit; LicenseCostFee --> Files

Figure 1. Feature model of Wiki engines by Acher et al. [2].

Table I
DECISION MODEL (TABULAR REPRESENTATION) OF THE DOPLER TOOL SUITE [6], [7] USING THE DOPLER NOTATION [3].

Id	Question	Type	Range	Card.	Constraints/Rules	Visible if
ALL	Do you want all standard Tools?	Bool	true false		if(ALL) { CW =true; DK =true; PK=true; }	true
CW	Do you want ConfigurationWizard (CW) for Product Derivation?	Bool	true false			!ALL
CW_authentication	Do you need authentication for product derivation?	Bool	true false			CW
... 6 more decisions related with CW's capabilities...						
CW_decisionboard	Include CW Decisionboard?	Bool	true false			CW
CW_views	Which of the following visualizations do you want to use during product derivation?	Enum	Table-based Tree-based Graph-based	1:3		CW
CW_wordgenerator	Include MS Word Generator for CW?	Bool	true false			CW
CW_wordgenerator_wordAddIn	Do you want editing support in MS Word to create variable documents?	Bool	true false			CW_wordgenerator
CW_guidance	How should guidance on decisions in ConfigurationWizard be displayed?	Enum	Always After first selection	1:1		CW
CW_resolution	Which default-resolution shall the CW have?	Enum	1280x1024 1900x1080 ...	1:1	if (1280x1024) { CW_res_width=1280.0; CW_res_height=1024.0; } if (1900x1080) { CW_res_width=1900.0; CW_res_height=1080.0; } ...	CW
CW_res_height		Double				false
CW_res_width		Double				false
DK	Do you want DecisionKing (DK) for variability modelling?	Bool	true false			!ALL
DK_builder	Include consistency checking support?	Bool	true false			DK
... 3 more decisions related with DK's capabilities...						
DK_modelconverter	Do you have old DOPLER models?	Bool	true false			PK DK
DK_sharepoint	Include sharepoint export support for developers?	Bool	true false			DK PK
PK	Do you want ProjectKing (PK) for derivation project management?	Bool	true false			!ALL
SERVER	Include DOPLER Server?	Bool	true false			true
ProprietaryTools	Include Proprietary Tools?	Bool	true false			CW DK

II. ALGORITHMS

We developed algorithms (see Algorithms 1–5) to transform a feature model such as the Wiki engines feature model (cf. Figure 1) into a decision model conforming to the DOPLER approach [3]. The function generateDecisionModel (cf. Algorithm 1) gets the root node of a feature model (f) and the set of constraints (constraints) as parameters and returns a set of

decisions. Procedure createDecisions (cf. line 3 of Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2) generates the decisions for all the features in depth-first manner (it recursively works its way through the feature hierarchy). For each feature it creates a decision. The feature name is used for the id and the question of the decision. For the id the feature name is extended by prefix d_ to distinguish decision ids from decision values.

Algorithm 1 From feature model to decision model.

```
1: function GENERATEDECISIONMODEL(f, constraints)
2:   decisions  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3:   createDecisions(decisions, f)
4:   createRules(decisions, constraints)
5:   return decisions
6: end function
```

All features are transformed into Boolean decisions (cf. decisions $d_{Unicode}$, $d_{Language}$ or d_{RSS} in Table II). The visibility of each decision is defined based on the feature hierarchy. The root feature (parent = \emptyset) becomes a decision (decision $d_{WikiMatrix}$ in Table II) with visibility true. Setting it to true means configuration of the model started and its rules (cf. deriveRules in Algorithm 5 and updateRules below) set all decisions representing mandatory child features to true. For each child feature its generated decision gets a visibility condition dependent on its parent feature (cf. Table II and how optional features are transformed). Special cases are mandatory features and features with a feature group relation to their parent. Mandatory features are out of scope of decision modeling [1] and consequently not visible to the user (decision visibility condition set to false; cf. decision d_{RSS} in Table II). For feature groups an enumeration decision is created with a value range for each selectable feature (cf. procedure createEnumDecisions in Algorithm 3) and rules setting the represented feature for each value to true, while its actual decision has its visibility condition set to false (cf. decision $d_{DifferentLicenses}$ of feature group LicenseCostFee and its enumeration decision $d_{LicenseCostFee_0}$ in Table II).

Function hasEnumType (cf. line 6 in Algorithm 2) determines if any children of a feature are part of an Or, Xor or Mutex group. Our algorithm transforms those feature groups into enumeration decisions (cf. decisions $d_{License_0}$, $d_{LicenseCostFee_0}$, $d_{Storage_0}$, and $d_{Language_0}$ in Table II). For this purpose, our algorithm uses the procedure createEnumDecisions of Algorithm 3, which iterates over each group of a feature. Similarly, function isEnumSubFeature (cf. line 21 in Algorithm 2) checks if the given feature is connected via a feature group to its parent. Child features of such a group become possible values (options) of the enumeration decision (using function defineRange in line 9 of Algorithm 3). If the parent feature of the feature group is optional, a None option is also additionally generated (cf. decisions $d_{LicenseCostFee}$, $d_{Storage}$, and $d_{Language}$ in Table II). The None option for optional features is necessary to allow developers not selecting the root feature of this feature group in the decision model (cf. how feature LicenseCostFee in Figure 1 is transformed into decisions $d_{LicenseCostFee}$ and $d_{LicenseCostFee_0}$ in Table II). If the root feature of the group is mandatory no None option is necessary, because a value has to be selected during derivation (cf. how feature License in Figure 1 is transformed in decision $d_{License}$ in Table II).

Function defineCardinality defines the cardinality of enumeration decisions. For Or groups the cardinality is defined as 1 to n, where n defines the number of options. For Xor groups a

Algorithm 2 Creating decisions from features.

```
1: procedure CREATEDECISIONS(d, f)
2:   decision  $\leftarrow$  new Decision(f.name)
3:   decision.type  $\leftarrow$  DType.Boolean
4:   decision.range  $\leftarrow$  {true}  $\cup$  {false}
5:   if hasEnumType(f) then
6:     createEnumDecisions(d, f)
7:   end if
8:   if f.parent =  $\emptyset$  then
9:     decision.visibility  $\leftarrow$  true
10:  else if f.type = CType.Mandatory then
11:    r  $\leftarrow$  deriveRule(d, f.parent.name, f.name, true)
12:    getDecision(d, f.parent.name).rules.add(r)
13:    updateRules(d, r)
14:    decision.visibility  $\leftarrow$  false
15:  else if isEnumSubFeature(f) then
16:    decision.visibility  $\leftarrow$  false
17:  else
18:    decision.visibility  $\leftarrow$  f.parent
19:  end if
20:  for child  $\in$  f.children do
21:    if !isEnumSubFeature(child) then
22:      createDecisions(d, child)
23:    end if
24:  end for
25:  d  $\leftarrow$  d  $\cup$  {decision}
26: end procedure
```

Algorithm 3 Feature groups are transformed into enumeration decisions.

```
1: procedure CREATEENUMDECISIONS(d, f)
2:   i  $\leftarrow$  0
3:   groups  $\leftarrow$  getEnumGroups(f)
4:   for group  $\in$  f.groups do
5:     decision  $\leftarrow$  new Decision(f.name + "_" + i)
6:     decision.question  $\leftarrow$  "Choose your "+ f.name
7:     decision.type  $\leftarrow$  DType.EnumType
8:     decision.cardinality  $\leftarrow$  defineCardinality(group)
9:     decision.range  $\leftarrow$  defineRange(group)
10:    decision.visibility  $\leftarrow$  f.name
11:    for option  $\in$  group do
12:      createDecisions(d, option)
13:      target  $\leftarrow$  getDecision(d, option.name)
14:      r  $\leftarrow$  deriveRule(d, option.name, target, true)
15:      decision.rules.add(r)
16:      updateRules(d, r)
17:    end for
18:    i  $\leftarrow$  i + 1
19:    d  $\leftarrow$  d  $\cup$  {decision}
20:  end for
21: end procedure
```

1 to 1 cardinality is defined as only one option can be selected and for Mutex groups a x to y cardinality is defined, where x and y are given by the Mutex defined in the feature model (cf. decision $d_{LicenseCostFee}$ in Table II). For each option a new decision is created using procedure createDecisions (cf. line 12 of Algorithm 3). Additionally, for each option a rule is defined, which sets the respective decision to true when being selected from the enumeration decision. The visibility of the decisions created for each option is false, causing those decisions not be shown to users during product derivation (as those decisions are selected via their "parent" enumeration decision).

Procedure createRules (cf. line 4 of Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 4) creates the rules from the different types of feature model constraints using procedure deriveRule (cf.

Table II

DECISION MODEL (TABULAR REPRESENTATION) GENERATED FROM THE WIKI ENGINES FEATURE MODEL (CF. FIGURE 1).

Id	Question	Type	Range	Card.	Constraints/Rules	Visible if
<i>d_WikiMatrix</i>	WikiMatrix?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_WikiMatrix</i>) { <i>d_RSS</i> =true; } if(<i>d_WikiMatrix</i>) { <i>d_License</i> =true; }	true
<i>d_RSS</i>	RSS?	Bool	true false			false
<i>d_Unicode</i>	Unicode?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Unicode</i>) { disAllow(<i>d_License_0.NoLimit</i>); disAllow(<i>d_Storage_0.None</i>); disAllow(<i>d_Language_0.None</i>) } if(! <i>d_Unicode</i>) { allow(<i>d_License_0.NoLimit</i>); allow(<i>d_Storage_0.None</i>); allow(<i>d_Language_0.None</i>) }	<i>d_WikiMatrix</i>
<i>d_WikiMatrix_0</i>	Choose your WikiMatrix	Enum	LicenseCostFee Storage	1:2	if(LicenseCostFee) { <i>d_LicenseCostFee</i> =true; } if(Storage) { <i>d_Storage</i> =true; }	<i>d_WikiMatrix</i>
<i>d_LicenseCostFee</i>	LicenseCostFee?	Bool	true false		if(! <i>d_LicenseCostFee</i>) { <i>d_LicenseCostFee_0.None</i> ; }	false
<i>d_Storage</i>	Storage?	Bool	true false		if(! <i>d_Storage</i>) { <i>d_Storage_0.None</i> ; }	false
<i>d_License</i>	License?	Bool	true false			false
<i>d_Language_0</i>	Language?	Bool	true false		if(! <i>d_Language</i>) { <i>d_Language_0.None</i> ; }	<i>d_WikiMatrix</i>
<i>d_License_0</i>	Choose your License	Enum	Commercial NoLimit GPL GPL2	1:1	if(Commercial) { <i>d_Commercial</i> =true; } if(NoLimit) { <i>d_NoLimit</i> =true; } if(GPL) { <i>d_GPL</i> =true; } if(GPL2) { <i>d_GPL2</i> =true; }	<i>d_License</i>
<i>d_Commercial</i>	Commercial?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Commercial</i>) { <i>d_LicenseCostFee_0.US</i> ; }	false
<i>d_NoLimit</i>	NoLimit?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_NoLimit</i>) { disAllow(<i>d_LicenseCostFee_0.DifferentLicenses</i>); <i>d_Unicode</i> = false; } if(! <i>d_NoLimit</i>) { allow(<i>d_LicenseCostFee_0.DifferentLicenses</i>); }	false
<i>d_GPL</i>	GPL?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_GPL</i>) { disAllow(<i>d_Storage_0.None</i>); disAllow(<i>d_LicenseCostFee_0.DifferentLicenses</i>); } if(! <i>d_GPL</i>) { allow(<i>d_Storage_0.None</i>); allow(<i>d_LicenseCostFee_0.DifferentLicenses</i>); }	false
<i>d_GPL2</i>	GPL2?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_GPL2</i>) { <i>d_Language_0.PHP</i> ; }	false
<i>d_LicenseCostFee_0</i>	Choose your LicenseCostFee	Enum	DifferentLicenses US Community None	0:1	if(DifferentLicenses) { <i>d_DifferentLicenses</i> =true; } if(US) { <i>d_US</i> =true; } if(Community) { <i>d_Community</i> =true; } if(!None) { disAllow(<i>d_Storage_0.Files</i>); } if(None) { allow(<i>d_Storage_0.Files</i>); }	<i>d_LicenseCostFee</i>
<i>d_DifferentLicenses</i>	DifferentLicenses?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_DifferentLicenses</i>) { disAllow(<i>d_License_0.GPL</i>); disAllow(<i>d_License_0.NoLimit</i>); } if(! <i>d_DifferentLicenses</i>) { allow(<i>d_License_0.GPL</i>); allow(<i>d_License_0.NoLimit</i>); }	false
<i>d_US</i>	US?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_US</i>) { <i>d_Language_0</i> = Java; <i>d_License_0</i> = Commercial; }	false
<i>d_Community</i>	Community?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Community</i>) { <i>d_Storage_0</i> = FileRCS; }	false
<i>d_Storage_0</i>	Choose your Storage	Enum	Files Database FileRCS None	1:1	if(Files) { <i>d_Files</i> =true; } if(Database) { <i>d_Database</i> =true; } if(FileRCS) { <i>d_FileRCS</i> =true; } if(!None) { <i>d_Unicode</i> = true; }	<i>d_Storage</i>
<i>d_Files</i>	Files?	Bool	true false		if(! <i>d_Files</i>) { <i>d_LicenseCostFee_0</i> = None; }	false
<i>d_Database</i>	Database?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Database</i>) { disAllow(<i>d_Language_0.Python</i>); } if(! <i>d_Database</i>) { allow(<i>d_Language_0.Python</i>); }	false
<i>d_FileRCS</i>	FileRCS?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_FileRCS</i>) { <i>d_Language_0</i> = Perl; <i>d_LicenseCostFee_0</i> = Community; }	false
<i>d_Language_0</i>	Choose your Language	Enum	Java Python PHP Perl None	1:1	if(Java) { <i>d_Java</i> =true; } if(Python) { <i>d_Python</i> =true; } if(PHP) { <i>d_PHP</i> =true; } if(Perl) { <i>d_Perl</i> =true; } if(!None) { <i>d_Unicode</i> = true; }	<i>d_Language</i>
<i>d_Java</i>	Java?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Java</i>) { <i>d_LicenseCostFee_0</i> = US; }	false
<i>d_Python</i>	Python?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Python</i>) { disAllow(<i>d_Storage_0.Database</i>); } if(! <i>d_Python</i>) { allow(<i>d_Storage_0.Database</i>); }	false
<i>d_PHP</i>	PHP?	Bool	true false			false
<i>d_Perl</i>	Perl?	Bool	true false		if(<i>d_Perl</i>) { <i>d_Storage_0</i> = FileRCS; }	false

Algorithm 5). Function `deriveRule` derives a DOPLER [3] rule from the constraint parameters. Bidirectional implies constraints are split into two unidirectional implies rules. Implies constraints (e.g., constraint `GPL2` implies `PHP`, cf. Figure 1) are transformed into decision rules in the form if decision (value) X then decision (value) Y (cf. Table II, where deci-

sion `d_GPL2` gets the rule if (`d_GPL2`) { `d_Language_0.PHP` }). If an implies constraint (e.g., the constraint `GPL` implies `Storage`, cf. Figure 1) regards an enumeration decision with option `None` (to reflect the fact that the original parent feature

Algorithm 4 Creating decision rules from feature model constraints.

```
1: procedure CREATERULES(d, constraints)
2:   for constraint ∈ constraints do
3:     cSource ← constraint.source.name
4:     cTarget ← constraint.target.name
5:     if constraint.type = CType.Implies then
6:       r ← deriveRule(d, cSource, cTarget, true)
7:       getDecision(d, cSource).rules.add(r)
8:       updateRules(d, r)
9:     else if constraint.type = CType.BiImplies then
10:      r ← deriveRule(d, cSource, cTarget, true)
11:      getDecision(d, cSource).rules.add(r)
12:      updateRules(d, r)
13:      r ← deriveRule(d, cTarget, cSource, true)
14:      getDecision(d, cTarget).rules.add(r)
15:      updateRules(d, r)
16:     else if constraint.type = CType.Excludes then
17:      r ← deriveRule(d, cSource, cTarget, false)
18:      getDecision(d, cSource).rules.add(r)
19:      updateRules(d, r)
20:      r ← deriveRule(d, cTarget, cSource, false)
21:      getDecision(d, cTarget).rules.add(r)
22:      updateRules(d, r)
23:     end if
24:   end for
25: end procedure
```

was optional), a decision rule with a disAllow function¹ is generated, that removes the None option (cf. rule if (GPL) { disAllow(*d_Storage*.None) } for decision *d_License* in Table II).

Excludes constraints affecting Boolean features are transformed into decision rules in the form if decision (value) X then decision (value) Y=false. Excludes constraints are bidirectional by default. Consequently, both ways have to be excluded (cf. NoLimit excludes Unicode in Figure 1 adding rules in decisions *d_NoLimit*). Similarly, if an excludes constraint (e.g., Unicode excludes NoLimit in Figure 1) affects an enumeration decision value, a decision rule using a disAllow function is created (cf. rule if (*d_Unicode*) { disAllow(*d_License_0*.NoLimit) } for decision *d_Unicode* in Table II). Another example is the excludes constraint LicenseCostFee excludes Files (cf. decision rule if(!None) { disAllow(*d_Storage*.Files) } in decision *d_LicenseCostFee_0* in Table II). Special cases are implies and excludes constraints for optional feature group parent features (that became enumeration decisions with an option None). For example, constraint Storage implies Unicode (cf. Figure 1) will be reflected by a decision rule, which involves the None option (cf. if (!None) { *d_Unicode* = true } for decision *d_Storage_0* in Table II).

The procedure updateRules adds new rules and detects and fixes any inconsistencies caused by introducing a new rule. For instance, for each decision rule with a disAllow function, a corresponding decision rule with an allow function² is generated. For example, if the *d_Unicode* decision is set to false or reset, *d_License.NoLimit* must become possible again. Another example are rules setting the None value in

¹removes a value set to an enumeration decision (if it has been set before) and removes the option from the set of allowed options.

²adds the decision option to the set of allowed options again.

enumeration decisions, when the parent decision is set to false (cf. rules in the decisions *d_LicenseCostFee*, *d_Storage* and *d_Language* in Table II). Further, the cardinality of each decision must be verified, to check none of them are violated by a rule. Existing consistency checkers [8] for decision models can be used.

Algorithm 5 Deriving rules from feature model constraints.

```
1: function DERIVERULE(d, sName, tName, isImplies)
2:   sd ← getDecision(d, sName)
3:   td ← getDecision(d, tName)
4:   ifCond ← sName
5:   action ← tName + "=false"
6:   if isEnumSubFeature(sd) && containsNoneOption(sd) then
7:     ifCond ← "!None"
8:   end if
9:   if isImplies then
10:    if isEnumSubFeature(td) && containsNoneOption(td) &&
        tName.equals(td.id) then
11:      action ← "disAllow(" + td + ".None)"
12:    else if isEnumSubFeature(td) then
13:      action ← td + "." + tName
14:    else
15:      action ← td + "=true"
16:    end if
17:  else
18:    if isEnumSubFeature(td) then
19:      action ← "disAllow(" + td + "." + tName + ")"
20:    else
21:      action ← td + "=false"
22:    end if
23:  end if
24:  r ← "if(" + ifCond + ") { " + action + " }"
25:  return r
26: end function
```

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